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CORRELATION BETWEEN JOB SATISFACTION AND ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOR

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This article reflects some selective results of the study on the subject of exploring the determinants of organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). It has been shown that the age of the employees and the participation in the staff meeting have a certain impact on the definition of the OCB. It has been confirmed that there is a positive correlation between "job satisfaction" and "organizational citizenship behavior", so the higher the job satisfaction, the more employees will exhibit organizational citizenship behavior.

Keywords: *organizational citizenship behavior, job satisfaction, correlation.*

CORELAȚIA DINTRE SATISFAȚIA ÎN MUNCĂ ȘI COMPORTAMENTUL ORGANIZAȚIONAL DE CETĂȚENIE

Prezentul articol reflectă unele rezultate selective ale studiului dedicat explorării determinantilor comportamentului de cetățenie organizațională (OCB). A fost demonstrat că vârsta angajaților și participarea la ședință a personalului au un anumit impact asupra definirii OCB. S-a confirmat că există o corelație pozitivă între „satisfacția în muncă” și „comportamentul de cetățenie organizațională”; astfel, cu cât mai mare este gradul de satisfacție în muncă, cu atât mai mulți angajați vor manifesta un comportament de cetățenie organizațională.

Cuvinte cheie: *comportament de cetățenie organizațională, satisfacție în muncă, corelare.*

Introduction

Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) impacts workgroup efficiency during the times of crisis (Organ, 1988) [1]. Job satisfaction plays an important role in contributing towards the OCB. Several authors mention in different context determinants of OCB, such as: Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment, Role Perceptions, Leadership Behavior and LMX, Fairness Perceptions, Individual Dispositions, Motivational Theories and Employee Age (Nadim and Muzahid, 2004) [2].

The research on work and organizational commitment offers mixed results. Early research by Buchanan [3] reinforced the belief that public sector managers have a lower level of organizational commitment than business executives. Similar findings have been reported by Rainey [4]. In a comparison of 474 Australian public sector employees and 944 private sector employees, Zeffane [5] found higher commitment among the latter. Moon [6] found that public sector managers have a lower level of organizational commitment than do private sector managers, especially in terms of their willingness to expand extra effort. Goulet and Frank [7] report the lowest organizational commitment among public sector employees and managers in a sample consisting of for-profit, nonprofit, and public sector employees and managers.

Some other studies, however, have reported a higher level of commitment among public sector managers or no difference. Farid (1997), for example, compared the organizational commitment of 54 and 43 middle managers from public sector and private sector organizations, respectively, and found no significant differences. Most studies report inconclusive or inconsistent findings [8].

In this context, the theoretical goal of our study is to examine the relationship between "job satisfaction" and "organizational citizenship behavior" (as significant factors to organizational success).

Research methodology

The study investigates the relationship between "job satisfaction" and "organizational citizenship behavior", and compares the terms of this relationship in the private sector and the public sector, using data collected from 109 participants.

Research tools: a questionnaire was created for the purposes of this study. It is comprised of multiple-choice questions (Likert scale), and divided into three parts (some questions were taken from relevant research in Hebrew or English): The first part includes questions regarding "job satisfaction" (MSQ), in which participants were asked to rate their satisfaction on a scale of 1 – 6 with 1 being 'not satisfied' and 6 being 'highly satisfied'.

Previous studies have yielded reasonable internal consistency coefficients – Cronbach's alpha (internal adapter) – for the overall satisfaction index, such as $\alpha = 0.86$. Items 1-20 examine the variable "satisfaction", and Cronbach's internal consistency coefficient α in this part of the questionnaire is $\alpha = 0.915$.

The second section regarding "organizational citizenship behavior" was defined in the questionnaire by a list of statements related to the phenomenon under investigation. Participants were asked to assess their level of agreement with each statement on a scale of 1-5 with a score of 5 indicating that the employee "strongly agrees" with the statement, while a score of 1 indicates that the employee "strongly disagrees" with the statement. As the statements regard employees' personal attitudes and positions, there was no "not relevant" option.

Research Findings

Difference between job satisfaction and organizational citizenship behavior

The variables in the questionnaire were measured with the use scales for several items / questions with the range of possible scores in the first questionnaire portion on "job satisfaction" ranging from 1 - 6, and from 1 - 5 in the second questionnaire portion on "organizational citizenship behavior". For the purposes of analysis, relevant answers were combined for each item to create one measurement – the average of responses in each scale. The average of the "job satisfaction" scale was $M = 4.787$ and the standard deviation; $Sd = 0.644$; The average of the "organizational citizenship behavior" scale was $M = 4.085$ and the standard deviation $Sd = 0.521$ (Fig.1).

Fig.1. Difference between job satisfaction and organizational citizenship behavior among total sample.

In light of current research literature, before the research hypotheses was tested, a trial was conducted to uncover whether there is a difference in the overall "job satisfaction" and "organizational citizenship behavior" averages between the private and public sectors. In order to test whether there is a significant difference a t-test for independent samples was conducted.

The results indicated a significant difference at 95 % certainty. The differences in job satisfaction averages in the different sectors presented as $t(107) = 3.799$, $p < 0.05$ (two – sided), while differences in organizational citizenship behavior averages are $t(107) = 6.472$, $p < 0.05$ (two – sided). Therefore, both the overall satisfaction averages and the organizational citizenship behavior averages showed a significant difference between the private and public sectors. Moreover, with the use of a t-test (one-sided), it became evident that the overall average of "job satisfaction" and the overall average of "organizational citizenship behavior" was higher in the public sector than the private sector.

Afterwards, differences between averages of both variables were examined between Public Sector vs. the Private Sector by independent t-test. This examination revealed that employees at Public Sector reported higher job satisfaction ($M=3.56$, $SD=1.23$) in comparison with employees at Private Sector ($M=2.21$, $SD=0.62$) ($t(52)=3.21$, $p<0.01$) (Fig.2).

Fig.2. Difference between public and private sectors at job satisfaction.

Moreover, employees at Public Sector reported higher organizational citizenship behavior ($M=4.02$, $SD=1.14$) in comparison with employees at Private Sector ($M=3.14$, $SD=1.22$) ($t(52)=4.82$, $p<0.01$) (Fig.3).

Fig.3. Difference between public and private sectors at organizational citizenship behavior.

Correlation between job satisfaction and organizational citizenship behavior

Hypothesis argues that there is a relationship between "job satisfaction" and "organizational citizenship behavior", such that the higher the degree of job satisfaction, the more organizational citizenship behavior employees will exhibit.

Due to the discovery that the internal consistency of all questions related to the "job satisfaction" variable is high, and the internal consistency of questions related to the "organizational citizenship behavior" variable is high, a total average variable could be determined separately for each variable. As these are two continuous variables, Pearson's correlation coefficient (two-sided) was used to determine whether there is a distinct correlation between the two.

The results uncovered a positive, strong, and significant correlation between employees' job satisfaction and organizational citizenship behavior, with 99% certainty, ($r(109) = 0.698$, $p < 0.01$). In order to examine job satisfaction factors that significantly contribute to organizational citizenship behavior, a multivariate regression analysis was conducted, with job satisfaction items (questions) as independent variables and the total average of organizational citizenship behavior as the dependent variable.

A one-way analysis by a variance (ANOVA) test uncovered a significant contribution at 95% certainty, with 73% explained variance. Variables that significantly contribute to organizational citizenship are (noted according to their level of significance to variance): a) "The way in which my place of employment enforces its policy"; b) "The opportunity to be constantly busy"; c) "The relationships among my colleagues"; d) "The opportunity to do things for others".

Correlation between Job Satisfaction and Organizational Citizenship Behavior, according to Age Group

In order to test the difference in the relationship between the variables in each age group, the intervening variable "age group" was consistent and Pearson's correlation coefficient (two - sided) was separately calculated for each age group. Results revealed a clear, positive, moderate to strong correlation in all age groups. However, there is an indication that the strength of the correlation among the adult age group (46-66) ($r(43) = 0.594$, $p < 0.01$), is slightly lower compared to the younger age group (36-45) ($r(35) = 0.784$, $p < 0.01$), with the latter being lower compared to the next-younger group (20-35) ($r(27) = 0.801$, $p < 0.01$) (Fig.4).

Fig.4. Difference between age groups at correlations of job satisfaction and organizational citizenship behavior.

Therefore, a negative correlation trend was found between the age group variable and the strength of the correlation between the two variables (job satisfaction and organizational citizenship behavior) - the older the age group, the more the strength of the correlation between the variables declines.

We further note that the t-test for independent variables uncovered a significant difference in the correlation between "job satisfaction" and "organizational citizenship behavior" in relationship to age – the older the age group, the more "job satisfaction" (independent variable).

Correlation between Job Satisfaction and Organizational Citizenship Behavior, according to Staff Meeting Participation

In order to examine the correlation between the variables "job satisfaction" and "organizational citizenship behavior" in relationship to staff meeting participation, items a-d in the relevant question were combined (Part C, Question 4 in the questionnaire) as "Participate in staff meetings" as opposed to item e, which was defined as "do not participate in staff meetings". The intervening variable "participation in staff meetings" was the consistent variable and Pearson's correlation coefficient (two - sided) was calculated separately for each group.

Results showed a distinct, positive, strong correlation with "job satisfaction" among the group of respondents who participate in staff meetings ($r(85) = 0.746$, $p < 0.01$) compared to those who do not participate in staff meetings ($r(22) = 0.545$, $p < 0.01$). Thus, the strength of the correlation increases with participation in staff meetings and taking an active part in collective thinking and decision-making (Fig.5).

Fig.5. Difference between participation at staff meetings at correlations of job satisfaction and organizational citizenship behavior.

A t-test of independent variables revealed a significant difference in “job satisfaction” between employees who participate in staff meetings and those who do not, such that employees who participate showed greater overall job satisfaction (independent variable) when compared to employees who do not participate in meetings.

Conclusions

Correlation was used to find the relationships among the determinants of OCB. Age of the employees and the Participation in Staff Meeting were found to have some impact on defining the OCB from the developing context. It has been confirmed that there is a positive correlation between “job satisfaction” and “organizational citizenship behavior”, so that the higher the degree of job satisfaction, the more employees will exhibit organizational citizenship behavior. This is exactly in line with the work conducted by Brown (1993) where he concluded by drawing a positive relationship between the two variables [9]. The findings can help organizations in devising the employee-focused strategies to stay competitive.

It is recommended to periodically conduct job analysis for various positions with the employees, in order to refresh consideration of role content, think about improvement, and consider promotion prospects and/ or mobilization, if necessary, in order to raise the level of job satisfaction and enhance the quality of teamwork and organizational efficiency.

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